

Sonographic Appearance of Gynecomastia Among Patients in University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan: A Retrospective Review

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ABSTRACT: Purpose: Gynecomastia, a benign proliferation of male breast glandular tissue, is a common condition affecting males across all ages and body types. This study aimed to review the demographic profile, clinical presentation, and sonographic characteristics of gynecomastia cases scanned at the Radiology Department, University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, and to provide data on sonographic characteristics and patterns of presentation in this population.

Methods: A retrospective review of all sonographically imaged cases of gynecomastia at UCH over 2 years was conducted. Clinical and demographic data, including age, BMI, marital status, breast laterality, prior breast disease, and histological subtype, were extracted from records. Data were analyzed in SPSS v27; frequencies and means were reported, and associations between categorical variables were assessed using the χ^2 test, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Results: A total of 30 male patients were included (mean age 37.4 years, range 8–79); 50% were >30 years, 26.7% were 18–30, and 23.3% <18. Mean BMI was 23.8 kg/m², with most patients in the normal range (43.3%), followed by overweight (26.7%), obese (16.7%), and underweight (13.3%). Marital status was evenly split, and over half had higher education. Most had no prior breast disease (86.7%), and nearly half presented subacutely (46.7%). Clinically, gynecomastia was diagnosed in 96.7%, mostly painless (83.3%) and bilateral (50%). Ultrasound confirmed gynecomastia in 76.7%, showing strong concordance with clinical diagnosis ($\chi^2 = 30.0$, $p < 0.001$); unilateral cases predominated on ultrasound (60.9%). Among the 23 patients with gynecomastia, the dendritic pattern was most frequent (47.8%), followed by nodular (39.1%) and diffuse glandular types (13%). There were no statistically significant associations between gynecomastia pattern and age ($\chi^2 = 2.254$, $p = 0.689$) or body mass index ($\chi^2 = 5.045$, $p = 0.538$).

Conclusion: Gynecomastia in this cohort commonly presented as true glandular enlargement across diverse ages and body types, with clinical examination demonstrating high reliability and ultrasound providing valuable confirmation and tissue characterization. Gynecomastia classification showed no significant association with age or body mass index, highlighting the limited predictive value of demographic and anthropometric factors.

Keywords: *Gynecomastia; Male breast enlargement; Histomorphology; Ultrasound; Simon classification; Nigeria*

Introduction

Gynecomastia is a benign enlargement of the male breast resulting from the proliferation of glandular breast tissue [1]. Clinically, it presents as a firm or rubbery mass concentric to the nipple–areolar complex and must be distinguished from pseudogynecomastia, which represents fatty deposition without glandular proliferation, commonly observed in obese individuals [2]. The term gynecomastia is derived from the Greek words *gyneka* (woman) and *mastos* (breast), reflecting its characteristic feminized appearance [3]. It is a common condition in the male population and is thought to be present in at least one-third of men over the course of

their lifetime [4]. It demonstrates a trimodal age distribution, occurring predominantly in neonates, adolescents, and elderly men [5].

The pathogenesis of gynecomastia is primarily related to an imbalance between estrogen and androgen activity, resulting either from increased estrogen levels, reduced androgen production, or an altered estrogen-to-androgen ratio [6]. While many cases are idiopathic or physiological, gynecomastia may also be associated with systemic illnesses such as chronic renal failure and liver disease, endocrine disorders including hypogonadism, genetic conditions such as Klinefelter's syndrome, and hormone-secreting tumors [2,6]. Several medications and substances have also been implicated, including methyldopa, flutamide, captopril, digitoxin, isoniazid, finasteride, spironolactone, and drugs of abuse [2]. The condition becomes more prevalent with advancing age due to declining testosterone levels and increasing rates of obesity [2].

Imaging aids in distinguishing gynecomastia from malignancy [7]. Radiographically, gynecomastia typically presents as a subareolar opacity or glandular tissue proliferation, often with a symmetrical distribution beneath the nipple. Recognition of characteristic imaging patterns is essential, as it improves diagnostic confidence and reduces unnecessary biopsies [8]. Three principal imaging patterns of gynecomastia have been consistently described in the literature: nodular, dendritic, and diffuse glandular, each reflecting varying stages of ductal and stromal proliferation [9]. The nodular pattern, often associated with early disease, appears mammographically as a fan- or wedge-shaped subareolar density. On ultrasound, it is typically visualized as a disc-shaped hypoechoic lesion that may demonstrate increased vascularity due to stromal proliferation [10]. In contrast, the dendritic pattern corresponds to the chronic or fibrotic phase and is usually observed in patients with longer symptom duration. Imaging characteristically reveals a flame-shaped retroareolar density with linear or finger-like projections extending into deeper adipose tissue, a feature considered largely irreversible because of the fibrotic component [10]. The diffuse glandular pattern resembles the heterogeneously dense appearance of a female breast and is commonly linked to sustained hormonal stimulation, including exogenous estrogen exposure [10].

Although gynecomastia is benign, it is a common source of anxiety and psychological distress among affected males due to fears of breast cancer, feminization, and social stigma [11,12]. These concerns may be exacerbated in environments where awareness is limited and patients are reluctant to seek medical attention. Clinically, gynecomastia may also represent the manifestation of an underlying pathological condition, making careful evaluation essential [13].

This study aims to review the sonographic characteristics and demographic profile of gynaecomastia cases diagnosed at the Radiology department, University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, and to compare the findings with other similar studies conducted locally and globally. It seeks to improve understanding of the appearance and characteristics of gynaecomastia in our environment.

Methods

A descriptive and retrospective review of all sonographically diagnosed cases of gynaecomastia at the Department of Radiology, University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, Nigeria, over a 2-year period from [April 2020 to March , 2022]. The University College Hospital is an 850-bed tertiary health facility and the oldest referral centre in the South-Western region of Nigeria, serving patients from Ibadan and surrounding areas, as well as referrals from other public and private hospitals.

Relevant clinical information, including patients' age, lesion laterality, and specific histological subtype of gynaecomastia, was retrieved from departmental records, sono-mammography books, and 54 request forms. Cases with incomplete or missing data were excluded from the study.

Breast imaging was performed on the cohort using a GE Voluson E ultrasound machine (GE USA Ltd, 2006) equipped with a 4–10MHz linear transducer. Both breasts were systematically scanned using B-mode ultrasound with linear probe for detailed evaluation of any lesions or asymmetries. Sonographic features recorded included lesion type: size, location, shape, margins, and echogenicity. Color Doppler was used as indicated to evaluate vascularity.

Data were entered and analysed using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics for Windows, version 27 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, New York, USA). Results were expressed as frequencies and means. The Chi-square test was used to assess associations between categorical variables, and a *p-value* of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Figure 1. A subareolar, fan -shaped US pattern of gynecomastia with surrounding fatty stroma in a 65 year old man patient

Figure 2. Sonographic appearance of dendritic Gynecomastia.

Figure 3. Sonographic appearance of Diffuse Gynecomastia.

Figure 4. Mammographic and Sonographic appearance of Nodular Gynecomastia.

Results

Among the 30 participants, the mean age was 37.4 years (range: 8–79), with half older than 30 years, 26.7% aged 18–30, and 23.3% younger than 18 (Figure 1). The mean BMI was 23.8 kg/m² (range: 15.6–33.2), with most participants having a normal BMI (43.3%), followed by overweight (26.7%), obese (16.7%), and underweight (13.3%) (Figure 2). Marital status was evenly split (50% single, 50% married) (Figure 3), and more than half had higher education (56.7%) (Figure 4). Most had no previous breast disease (86.7%), and nearly half presented with a subacute condition (46.7%) (Figures 5 & 6).

Clinically, the vast majority were diagnosed with gynecomastia (96.7%), with only 3.3% as pseudogynecomastia. Most patients were painless (83.3%), though 16.7% reported pain, and breast swelling occurred in 63.3%. Bilateral lumps were most common (50%), followed by right (26.7%) and left-sided lumps (3.3%), with 20% having no palpable lump. Nipple discharge and positive family history were rare (3.3% and 6.7%, respectively) (Table 2).

Ultrasound confirmed gynecomastia in 23 patients (76.7%), pseudogynecomastia in 1 (3.3%), and no gynecomastia in 6 (20%) (Figure 7). Clinical diagnosis strongly agreed with ultrasound findings ($\chi^2 = 30.0$, $p < 0.001$) (Table 3). Most patients

showed that the dendritic pattern (47.8%), followed by the nodular pattern (39.1%) and diffuse glandular pattern (13.0%), while a large majority of cases (86.7%) presented with axillary nodes in the right and left breast, with only 13.3% showing none (Table 4).

Analysis of unilateral and bilateral gynecomastia by age group and BMI showed no significant associations, although unilateral involvement was more common in patients older than 30 years and those with normal or overweight BMI, while bilateral gynecomastia appeared relatively more frequent among obese patients ($p = 0.448$ for age; $p = 0.293$ for BMI) (Table 5). Among patients with ultrasound-confirmed gynecomastia, unilateral disease predominated, affecting 14 patients (60.9%), compared with 9 patients (39.1%) with bilateral involvement (Figure 8).

In addition, among the 23 patients with gynecomastia, the dendritic pattern was the most common (47.8%), followed by nodular (39.1%) and diffuse glandular types (13%) (Figure 9). Comparison across age groups showed no significant association between gynecomastia classification and age ($\chi^2 = 2.254$, $p = 0.689$), although dendritic cases were more frequently observed in patients older than 30 years. Likewise, there was no statistically significant relationship between gynecomastia pattern and body mass index ($\chi^2 = 5.045$, $p = 0.538$). Nodular gynecomastia occurred mainly among individuals with normal BMI, dendritic cases were distributed across BMI categories with a slight predominance in overweight patients.

Discussion

In this study of 30 male patients presenting with breast enlargement, we observed a broad age range, with a mean of 37.4 years and representation across adolescents, young adults, and older men (Figure 5). Although this mean age is slightly lower than that reported by Ajani et al.¹³ (43.36 years), it still reflects the well-known bimodal pattern of gynecomastia, peaking during puberty and later adulthood due to hormonal fluctuations, aging, and metabolic changes. Population-based studies show that transient gynecomastia is common in boys, while it persists as a frequent finding in the general male population [14].

The BMI distribution in this cohort, with most participants in the normal range and smaller proportions being overweight or obese (Figure 6), highlights the multifactorial influences on gynecomastia. While some imaging studies suggest that radiologic measures of breast tissue do not always correlate directly with BMI, obesity is known to contribute to relative estrogen excess through peripheral aromatization of androgens in adipose tissue [15]. The even marital distribution (Figure 7) and high rate of higher education (Figure 8) likely reflect the patient population we serve and their health-seeking behaviors, rather than any direct biological effect on gynecomastia.

Clinically, the vast majority of patients were diagnosed with true gynecomastia (96.7%), with only a small fraction having pseudogynecomastia. Most patients had no pain (83.3%), with pain reported in only 16.7%, which is consistent with other series where aesthetic concerns outweigh discomfort. In multicenter adult studies, mild discomfort and cosmetic worry were the most common reasons for seeking care, with pain reported in roughly half of cases [16]. Breast swelling was common, and bilateral involvement predominated, in line with prior reports where bilateral gynecomastia is more frequent than unilateral [16]. Nipple discharge and a positive family history were rare, as expected given the largely benign nature of the condition.

Ultrasonography confirmed gynecomastia in 23 patients (76.7%), with only a few cases showing pseudogynecomastia or no sonographic evidence (Figure 11). The high concordance between clinical and ultrasound diagnoses ($\chi^2 = 30.0$, $p < 0.001$) supports the value of ultrasound as a reliable tool, particularly when physical findings are unclear. Ultrasound is useful for distinguishing glandular proliferation from adipose-predominant changes, with typical patterns such as flame-shaped or heterogeneous retroareolar tissue well documented in prior studies [17].

Ultrasonographic breast patterns showed notable axillary lymph node involvement in the majority of patients (Table 11). Previous research emphasizes that recognizing the spectrum of benign sonographic appearances is important to avoid unnecessary biopsies, as gynecomastia is overwhelmingly benign and male breast cancer is rare

(<1%) [18]. The reactive appearance of most lymph nodes likely reflects benign inflammatory changes rather than malignancy.

Unilateral gynecomastia was more common than bilateral involvement (60.9% vs. 39.1%), although no significant associations with age or BMI were found (Table 5, Figure 12). This corresponds with Ajani et al.¹³ whose study in same tertiary health setting found unilateral gynecomastia (either left or right, but not both) in 66% of the cases. While some larger studies suggest that unilateral or bilateral patterns may relate to disease duration or BMI, these associations often do not reach statistical significance without larger sample sizes [16].

The predominance of the dendritic pattern in this study is consistent with well-established radiologic descriptions of gynecomastia, where the dendritic form is commonly associated with longstanding disease as a result of progressive stromal fibrosis and ductal proliferation [2,7]. This observation is further supported by the fact that most patients presented with either subacute (46.7%) or chronic (26.7%) symptoms. Sarica et al.⁷ similarly reported a higher occurrence of dendritic gynecomastia among patients with longer symptom duration, noting that individuals with symptoms lasting 1–2 years showed more dendritic (70%) than diffuse patterns (30%), while those with symptoms under one year still demonstrated a predominance of dendritic morphology compared with the nodular type (92.3% vs. 1.9%). The relatively high proportion of nodular gynecomastia in the present cohort also aligns with earlier evidence that this subtype typically reflects the florid, early phase of the condition, a category into which 16.7% of the cases in this study fall.

The absence of a statistically significant association between gynecomastia pattern and age is in keeping with contemporary imaging literature suggesting that morphologic subtypes are more reflective of disease stage than of fixed demographic boundaries. Imaging studies describe nodular, dendritic, and diffuse patterns as progressive phases characterized by varying degrees of stromal and ductal proliferation, with dendritic morphology often emerging after symptoms persist for more than one year, indicating temporal evolution rather than direct age dependence [10]. Although gynecomastia occurs across a wide adult age range, for instance, a sonographic cohort spanning 24–74 years demonstrated multiple pattern types within

the same population [5], these findings reinforce the view that subtype distribution is not inherently age-restricted [19].

Similarly, the lack of a significant relationship between gynecomastia pattern and BMI supports existing evidence that true gynecomastia is primarily hormonally mediated rather than driven solely by adiposity. A clinical comparison of gynecomastia and pseudogynecomastia found that true glandular enlargement is associated with a higher estradiol-to-testosterone ratio, highlighting endocrine imbalance as a central mechanism independent of body habitus [20]. Moreover, sonographic evaluation differentiates pseudogynecomastia from true glandular disease, which accounted for only 8% of cases in one imaging cohort [19], emphasizing the importance of distinguishing adipose enlargement from genuine ductal proliferation, particularly in populations experiencing rising obesity rates.

Finally, the distribution of diffuse glandular gynecomastia should be interpreted with caution due to the small number of cases, which limits statistical power and broader applicability. Nevertheless, the overall pattern observed highlights the heterogeneous nature of gynecomastia and underscores the diagnostic value of imaging in accurately characterizing disease stage.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings above, this study provides a clear picture of how gynecomastia presents in our patient population. It affects males across all ages and body types, most often appearing as true, sometimes bilateral glandular enlargement. Clinical examination proved highly reliable, and ultrasound added useful detail on tissue patterns and lymph node involvement, helping to confirm the diagnosis. The type of gynecomastia did not seem to depend on age or body mass. Overall, these findings contribute to the growing body of evidence that, although demographic and anthropometric variables may influence clinical presentation, they do not reliably predict radiologic subtype. Future studies with larger cohorts are recommended to further clarify potential associations and strengthen the external validity of these observations.

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Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Age and BMI

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	30	8	79	37.40	23.363
BMI	30	15.59	33.15	23.7766	5.00658
Valid N (listwise)	30				

Table 2: Patient Diagnostic Information Table

Assessments	Categories	Frequency (%)
Clinical Diagnosis	Gynecomastia	29 (96.7)
	Pseudogynecomastia	1 (3.3)
Patients' Symptoms		
Pain	No	25 (83.3)
	Yes	5 (16.7)
Swelling	No	11 (36.7)
	Yes	19 (63.3)
Lump	None	6 (20.0)
	Left breast lump	1 (3.3)
	Right breast lump	8 (26.7)
	Bilateral	15 (50.0)
Nipple discharge	No	29 (96.7)
	Yes	1 (3.3)
Family History	No	28 (93.3)
	Yes	2 (6.7)

Table 3: Similarities Between Ultrasound Finding and Clinical Diagnosis

Predictors	Sub-categories	Ultrasound Finding			χ^2	P value
		Gynecomastia (23)	Pseudogynecomastia (1)	Non-gynecomastia (6)		
Clinical Diagnosis	Gynecomastia	23 (100.0)	-	6 (100.0)	30.000	<0.001*
	Pseudogynecomastia	-	1 (100.0)	-		

Table 4: USS findings patterns

	Categories	Frequency (%)
Ultrasound Pattern	Nodular	9 (39.1)
	Dendritic	11 (47.8)
	Diffuse glandular	3 (13.0)
Axillary Nodes Rt and Lt breast	No	4 (13.3)
	Yes	26 (86.7)

Table 5: Distribution of Unilateral and Bilateral Gynecomastia

Predictors	Sub-categories	Ultrasound Finding		χ^2	P value
		Unilateral (18)	Bilateral (12)		
Age Group	<18 years	3 (16.7)	4 (33.3)	1.607	0.448
	18-30 years	6 (33.3)	2 (16.7)		
	>30 years	9 (50.0)	6 (50.0)		
BMI	Underweight	2 (11.1)	2 (16.7)	3.726	0.293
	Normal	7 (38.9)	6 (50.0)		
	Overweight	7 (38.9)	1 (8.3)		
	Obese	2 (11.1)	3 (25.0)		

Table 6: Distribution of Classification of Gynecomastia

Predictors	Sub-categories	Classification of Gynecomastia			χ^2	P value
		Nodular (9)	Dendritic (11)	Diffuse Glandular (3)		
Age Group	<18 years	2 (22.2)	3 (27.3)	1 (33.3)	2.254	0.689
	18-30 years	3 (33.3)	1 (9.1)	1 (33.3)		
	>30 years	4 (44.4)	7 (63.6)	1 (33.3)		
BMI	Underweight	1 (11.1)	3 (27.3)	-	5.045	0.538
	Normal	4 (44.4)	2 (18.2)	2 (66.7)		
	Overweight	3 (33.3)	4 (36.4)	-		
	Obese	1 (11.1)	2 (18.2)	1 (33.3)		